

MESOSCOPIC MODELING OF CROSSLINKED THERMOSET RESIN USING DISSIPATIVE PARTICLE DYNAMICS

TOHOKU
UNIVERSITY

Yoshiaki Kawagoe¹,

Gota Kikugawa²

Tomonaga Okabe¹³⁴

¹ Department of Aerospace Engineering, Tohoku University, Japan

² Institute of Fluid Science, Tohoku University, Japan

³ Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Washington, USA

⁴ Polymer Matrix Hybrid Composite Materials Group, National Institute for Materials Science, Japan

Soft Matter

PAPER

Cite this: *Soft Matter*, 2021, 17, 6707

Thermoset resin curing simulation using quantum-chemical reaction path calculation and dissipative particle dynamics

Yoshiaki Kawagoe,^{†*} Gota Kikugawa,^{†*} Keiichi Shirasu[†] and Tomonaga Okabe^{†*}

Thermoset resin

- Main component of the matrix resin for CFRP
- Crosslinking network is formed via chemical reaction
- Toughness and durability of CFRP strongly depend on those properties of the matrix resin

- ✓ There are numerous combinations of base resin and curing agent.
- ✓ It is impossible to obtain the physical properties of all combinations experimentally, and screening by using numerical techniques is necessary.
- ✓ Numerical methods that can express material properties derived from molecular and atomic structures are required.

Molecular-based simulations (e.g. Molecular dynamics simulations, MD) are useful.

For thermoset resin ...

- ✓ Chemical reactions
- ✓ Dynamics in condensed matter
- ✓ Heat of formation and its dispersion

It is necessary to consider multi-timescale and multi-physics, such as reaction, dynamics, and heat dispersion.

- ※ This algorithm was implemented in Materials Studio and J-OCTA
- ※ This algorithm can be used coupling with LAMMPS

All-atom MD can only capture phenomena on the scale of tens of nm and tens of ns.

Vidil, Progress in Polymer Science 62 (2016) 126–179

Mesoscopic coarse/fine crosslinking distribution
→ it may form fracture origins

Large-scale and long-timescale curing simulation methods are needed to investigate mesoscopic phenomena

Odagiri, Materials System 37 (2020) 29-35

Thermoset/thermoplastic blend forms reaction-induced phase separations

Dissipative Particle Dynamics (DPD)

- DPD simulation is a coarse-grained simulation method that has been used to investigate mesoscale phenomena such as biomolecular motion and spinodal decomposition.
- A single DPD bead represents several atoms and, thus, larger systems can be simulated over longer periods

Ala_{15} helical conformation of MD and DPD.
 Kumar, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, **124** (2020), 11379–11386

DPD simulations for the SPEEK/PVDF-g-PSSA blends
 Ma, *RSC Adv.*, **7** (2017), 39676–39684

Global reaction route mapping (GRRM), is an accurate reaction-path search package aided by ab initio quantum calculations using the Gaussian program.

Calculated properties:

- ① Activation energy, E_a
- ② Heat of formation, H_f

Newton's equation

$$m_i \frac{d\mathbf{v}_i}{dt} = \mathbf{f}_i$$

A single DPD bead represents several atoms

Interactions

$$\mathbf{f}_i = \sum_{j \neq i} \left(\mathbf{F}_{ij}^C + \mathbf{F}_{ij}^D + \mathbf{F}_{ij}^R \right) + \sum_{\text{bonds with } i} \mathbf{F}_i^B + \sum_{\text{angles with } i} \mathbf{F}_i^A$$

Conservative force: $\mathbf{F}_{ij}^C = -\frac{\partial V^C}{\partial \mathbf{r}_{ij}} = a_{ij} \frac{1}{r_c} \left(1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{r_c} \right) \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} H(r_c - r_{ij})$

Repulsion parameter

Dissipative force: $\mathbf{F}_{ij}^D = -\gamma \omega^D(r_{ij}) (\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} \cdot \mathbf{v}_{ij}) \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} H(r_c - r_{ij})$

Random force: $\mathbf{F}_{ij}^R = \sigma \omega^R(r_{ij}) \zeta_{ij} \Delta t^{-1/2} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} H(r_c - r_{ij})$

$$\sigma^2 = 2\gamma k_B T$$

$$\omega^D(r_{ij}) = \left[\omega^R(r_{ij}) \right]^2 = \left(1 - \frac{r_{ij}}{r_c} \right)^2$$

Bond stretching: $V_{ij}^B = k_{ij} (r_{ij} - r_0)^2$

Angle bending: $V_{ijk}^A = k_{ijk} (\theta_{ijk} - \theta_0)^2$

DPD particles are coarse-grained based on functional groups before and after the reaction

The repulsion and intramolecular interaction parameters of DPD are determined from the preliminary all-atom MD simulations, the solubility parameters and Flory–Huggins theory.

Here, we used the values from Kacar et al.^{1,2}

The activation energy and heat of formation were calculated using GRRM.

Table : E_a and H_f (B3LYP/6-31G(d))

	E_a [kcal/mol]	H_f [kcal/mol]
Epoxy/primary amine (A/D)	46.56	26.60
Epoxy/secondary amine at corner (A/D')	43.23	23.46
Epoxy/secondary amine at center (A/E)	46.68	22.15

Simulation conditions

DGEBA 200 molecules, DETA 80 molecules
(DPD: 1240 particles, AA-MD: 11400 atoms)

Curing temperature : 50 °C

Acceleration constant: 10^{19}

Reaction cutoff: 5.64 Å

¹G. Kacar, et al., *Epl*, **102** (2013), 40009; ²G. Kacar, et al., *J. Phys. Chem. C*, **117** (2013), 19038

Flow of curing simulation

Relaxation DPD (in-house code)

- Temperature: 50 °C
- Times step 69.3 fs
- Relaxation time: 173 ps/cycle
- Periodic boundary conditions
- Box size: 51.2 × 51.2 × 51.2 Å³

Cross-linking (python)

$$\text{Conversion rate}[\%] = \frac{\text{Number of reacted epoxy groups}}{\text{Number of total epoxy groups}} \times 100$$

Run-time:

Curing AA-MD : 52.7 hours (200 cores)

Curing DPD : 400 sec (20 cores)

→ 1/480 (run-time)

→ 1/10 (computational-resource)

To evaluate the precise material properties of the thermoset resin, an all-atom system is reconstructed from a coarse-grained system.

- ✓ Center of mass
- ✓ Rotation by \mathbf{R}
- ✓ Energy minimization

(a) DPD system

(b) Reconstructed AA-MD system

Rotation of AA fragment

$$\mathbf{d}_{\text{DPD}} = \mathbf{R}\mathbf{d}_{\text{AA}} = \left(2\frac{\mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^T}{\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{s}} - \mathbf{I} \right) \mathbf{d}_{\text{AA}},$$

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{d}_{\text{DPD}} + \mathbf{d}_{\text{AA}}$$

Comparison of thermomechanical properties of
 AA-atom resin model obtained in curing MD simulation and
 AA-atom resin model reconstructed from DPD model

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns:

$$\frac{I_{\text{coh}}(q)}{N} = \sum_{i=1}^n c_i f_i^2(q) + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n c_i c_j f_i(q) f_j(q) \left(S_{ij}^{\text{FZ}}(q) - 1 \right),$$

Fig. 7 Comparison of coherent scattering intensity obtained from fully cured AA-MD and reconstructed AA-MD simulations with the experimental values.⁶²

[62] Lin, Polymer **34** (1993) 277–288

$f_i(q)$ is the atomic scattering factor

$$S_{ij}^{\text{FZ}}(q) = n_0 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} 4\pi r^2 (g_{ij}(r) - 1) \frac{\sin qr}{qr} dr + 1.$$

$$g_{\alpha\beta}(r) = \frac{N_{\alpha\beta}(r)}{4\pi r^2 n_{\beta} dr},$$

- ✓ First peak ($q = 0.3\text{--}0.4 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$)
Local ordered structure attributed to two-dimensional growth in curing
- ✓ Second peak ($q = 1.25 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$)
Typical amorphous halo attributed to intermolecular correlations.

Curing simulation of large system
(250 Å × 250 Å × 250 Å)

Reaction-induced phase separation of
thermoset/thermoplastic blend

We propose a curing simulation technique involving a dissipative particle dynamics (DPD) simulation, which can simulate a larger system and longer time period than those of conventional all-atom molecular dynamics (AA-MD) simulations.

- ✓ The proposed curing DPD simulation can represent the exothermic reaction process precisely by considering each reactivity calculated via quantum-chemical calculations.
- ✓ The cure reaction process given by the curing DPD simulation agrees well with that given by a conventional curing AA-MD simulation, but with run-time and computational-resource reductions of 1/480 and 1/10 times, respectively.
- ✓ The X-ray diffraction pattern and thermomechanical properties of the reconstructed all-atom system agree well with those of the experimental results.
- ✓ The proposed curing simulation technique can be applied in high-throughput screening and in large system calculations for mesoscopic phenomena.

Thank you for your kind attention.